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CONTEXT

Objectives:

- Improve **knowledge and management of mobility flows** among a range of transport modes
- Enable the **implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions**, services, and business models
- **Move traffic management** from traditional managing of traffic volumes to **handling different types of available vehicles**

The **TANGENT project** is developing **new complementary tools for optimising traffic operations**, elaborating data related to multimodal transport services and considering automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport

THE PROBLEM

What: A governance model for managing and facilitating data sharing between the different stakeholders involved in the TANGENT project

Why: Data from heterogeneous data sources **must be appropriately shared between the stakeholders** involved in the project to enable the development and testing of the TANGENT services for optimising multimodal traffic operations

How: The TANGENT project defines a methodology for formalising the **Data Sharing Governance model based on an extensive analysis of the literature and the adoption of best practices** and adequately managing and facilitating data-sharing tasks

METHODOLOGY

- BEST PRACTICES**
- Definition of **rules** and establishment of a **Technical Management Board** for facilitating the processes of data collection, publication, and sharing
 - Definition of a **metadata catalogue** for supporting the data-sharing
 - Definition of **rules to enforce compliance** with European regulations on data and to **ensure interoperability and reuse** of data and metadata
 - Definition of rules to properly **govern data manipulation**
 - Definition of rules to properly **govern data reuse**

- FEEDBACKS**
- Adoption of a **metadata profile** for describing datasets
 - Define **NDA**s with **external data providers** to enable and regulate access to and the use of private datasets
 - Assure a **high level of data quality** of the dataset
 - Ensure **compliance with existing licenses** for handling dataset access, manipulation and use

TANGENT DATA SHARING GOVERNANCE MODEL

KEY ASPECTS

- Data governance is characterized by **different objectives**
- Data governance should consider **different data source types**
- Data governance should consider **different tools and technologies** adopted for data-sharing
- Data governance refers to **different processes**
- Different actors with **different roles** are involved in the governance of each process
- **Different rules** should be applied to establish effective data governance

5 PROCESSES

- **Data publication:** the process of describing a data source in a shared catalogue using a metadata profile
- **Data quality:** the process of assessing the quality of a data source and its metadata
- **Data access:** the process of accessing data contained in or exposed from a data source
- **Data storage:** the process of storing (a portion of) data provided from a data source
- **Data usage:** the process of using and/or manipulating data from one or more data sources

PROCESSES, ROLES, TOOLS AND RULES

CONTACT INFORMATION

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